

COMPARATIVE PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF MONOCRYSTALLINE, POLYCRYSTALLINE, AND THIN-FILM SOLAR PANELS UNDER VARYING SOLAR IRRADIANCE IN ABAKALIKI, EBONYI STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the comparative performance of monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and thin-film solar panels under varying solar irradiance and temperature conditions. The study employed an experimental design in which photovoltaic panels were exposed to natural sunlight during a seven-day rooftop experiment in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State, Nigeria, with measurements of solar irradiance, ambient temperature, voltage, current, and power output. All the panels were operated at a uniform tilt equal to the site's latitude and the same orientation, with identical cleaning and maintenance procedures to ensure consistent solar exposure. Results show that monocrystalline panels achieved the highest mean power output (53.80 ± 15.05 W), voltage (18.49 ± 0.20 V), and current (2.91 ± 0.80 A), outperforming polycrystalline (45.69 ± 14.11 W; 17.73 ± 0.21 V; 2.57 ± 0.77 A) and thin-film panels (32.03 ± 10.24 W; 16.03 ± 0.34 V; 2.00 ± 0.65 A). The study concluded that monocrystalline panels have more technological advantage due to their higher and more consistent power output, voltage stability, and responsiveness to varying solar irradiance, making them better suited for energy-demanding applications, especially in warm, high-irradiance regions like Nigeria.

Keywords: Comparative performance, Monocrystalline, Polycrystalline, Thin-film

1. Introduction

Over the last few decades, the growing threat of climate change and depletion of fossil fuel reserves have led to a global shift toward renewable energy as a sustainable alternative for power generation. Among the various forms of renewable energy sources, solar energy has emerged as one of the most promising due to its abundance, reliability, and relatively low environmental impact. According to the International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA, 2021), solar power accounted for over 30% of all new renewable energy

installations in 2020 alone, with an increasing trend expected to continue across both developed and developing nations. Solar energy technology plays a critical role in the effort to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, addresses energy poverty, and ensures long-term environmental sustainability (Izamet *et al.*, 2022; Katoch *et al.*, 2024). Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, which convert sunlight directly into electricity, have gained considerable attention in energy research and policy (Sampaio and González, 2017). These systems are predominantly made up of three major types of panels: monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and thin-film. Each of these

panel types differs in their material structure, cost of production, efficiency levels, and response to environmental conditions (Yang *et al.*, 2024). Monocrystalline panels are typically more efficient and expensive, while polycrystalline panels offer a cost-effective balance. Thin-film panels, on the other hand, are flexible and lightweight but generally less efficient (Dallaevet *et al.*, 2023). The understanding of how each of these technologies performs under varying environmental factors such as solar irradiance and temperature is vital in selecting the most suitable type for different geographical locations and applications (Issaadiet *et al.*, 2018). The performance of solar panels is significantly influenced by external conditions, particularly temperature and solar irradiance, which vary naturally across time and space (Shaker *et al.*, 2024). High irradiance generally leads to higher energy production, while temperature can have both positive and negative effects on efficiency depending on the panel type (Mohammed *et al.*, 2024). In regions with high solar potential such as Sub-Saharan Africa, the opportunity to harness solar energy to meet domestic and industrial energy needs is immense, yet often underutilized due to limited performance data and poor system optimization. Nigeria, for instance, receives an average solar radiation of about 5.5 kWh/m²/day, but its adoption of solar PV systems remains significantly below potential due to issues surrounding efficiency, cost, and technology choices (Unegbu *et al.*, 2024). This has necessitated the need for local, comparative performance analysis of available solar panel types under real-world operating conditions. Empirical studies that evaluate the impact of varying solar irradiance and ambient temperature on different PV technologies are

crucial to making informed choices in the deployment of solar infrastructure. Such evaluations will not only enhance the effective planning and integration of solar energy systems into the national grid, but also inform policy direction and investment decisions in the renewable energy sector (Mohammed *et al.*, 2024; Mahim *et al.*, 2024).

In view of this, the present study seeks to investigate and compare the performance of monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and thin-film solar panels under varying solar irradiance and temperature conditions. This will provide evidence-based recommendations for improving solar energy utilization in Nigeria and other developing nations.

2. Methodology

Study Location and Duration

The experimental campaign was conducted over a continuous seven-day period in June 2025 at a rooftop test site in Abakaliki, Ebonyi State Nigeria (latitude 6.32485° N, longitude 8.11368° E) The site was selected for its unobstructed solar access and minimal shading throughout daylight hours. Daily measurements were taken between 011:00 and 16:00 local time to capture peak irradiance and typical operating temperatures.

Solar Panel Specifications

Three commercially available photovoltaic panels were evaluated:

- **Monocrystalline silicon** (rated 60 W, 18.5 V nominal voltage)
- **Polycrystalline silicon** (rated 60 W, 17.8 V nominal voltage)

- **Thin-film cadmium telluride (CdTe)** (rated 60 W, 16.0 V nominal voltage) were averaged to produce a single daily mean for each parameter (see Table 1 and Table 2).

All panels had active surface areas of 0.41 m² and were mounted at a fixed tilt angle equal to the site’s latitude. Manufacturer datasheets were consulted to verify nominal performance characteristics.

2.3 Instrumentation and Data Acquisition

- **Solar irradiance** was recorded using a Class A pyranometer (Model ISO 9060, accuracy ± 5 W/m²), mounted adjacent to the panels at the same tilt angle.
- **Ambient temperature** was logged via a shielded thermistor (Model KT-908 ± 0.5 °C) positioned 1 m above the panel surface.
- **Voltage (V) and current (A)** outputs from each panel were measured with a calibrated digital multimeter (Model M890C $\pm 0.1\%$ accuracy).
- **Power output (W)** was calculated as the instantaneous product of measured voltage and current.

Data were sampled at 30-minute intervals, yielding 14 readings per panel per day. Values

Results

Table 1: Daily Environmental Conditions and Power Output of Three Solar Panel Types

Summary of solar irradiance, ambient temperature, and daily power output for monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and thin-film panels over a 7-day period

Day	Solar Irradiance (W/m ²)	Temperature (°C)	Monocrystalline (W)	Polycrystalline (W)	Thin-Film (W)
1	543.5	39.3	53.89	42.91	32.71
2	313.4	39.5	29.39	24.39	15.7
3	580.8	29.4	53.5	42.93	32.99
4	429.8	32.7	39.58	34.32	23.4
5	744.8	31.6	65.96	57.2	37.18

2.4 Experimental Procedure

At the start of each measurement day, all panels were cleaned with deionized water to remove dust and ensure consistent surface conditions. The panels were connected to their respective multimeters via low-resistance leads. The pyranometer and thermistor were zeroed and validated according to manufacturer instructions. Readings were recorded manually and cross-checked against a data logger’s secondary record to minimize transcription errors.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

The daily means of voltage, current, and power output for each panel type were computed. Table 3 presents the overall means and standard deviations (SD) across the seven-day period. Data was analyzed and visualized using python.

1. **Descriptive statistics** (mean \pm SD) to quantify central tendency and variability.

6	655.4	27.8	61.77	51.69	34.22
7	838.7	30.4	72.51	66.39	47.99

Table 2: Daily Voltage and Current Output of Monocrystalline, Polycrystalline, and Thin-Film Solar Panels

Recorded daily voltage and current values for each panel type, reflecting electrical performance trends across the 7-day study duration.

Panel Type	Measure	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6	Day 7
Monocrystalline	Voltage (V)	18.69	18.36	18.20	18.34	18.50	18.72	18.60
	Current (A)	2.88	1.60	2.94	2.16	3.57	3.30	3.90
Polycrystalline	Voltage (V)	17.73	17.66	17.53	17.45	18.05	17.77	17.90
	Current (A)	2.42	1.38	2.45	1.97	3.17	2.91	3.71
Thin-Film	Voltage (V)	16.47	16.07	16.44	15.82	16.06	15.56	15.80
	Current (A)	1.99	0.98	2.01	1.48	2.31	2.20	3.04

Table 3: Average Voltage, Current, Power Output, and Operating Temperature of Solar Panels (Mean ± Standard Deviation)

Comparison of mean electrical performance and temperature across panel types, including variability indicators.

Panel Type	Voltage (V)	Current (A)	Power (W)	Temperature (°C)
Monocrystalline	18.49 ± 0.20	2.91 ± 0.80	53.80 ± 15.05	32.96 ± 4.67
Polycrystalline	17.73 ± 0.21	2.57 ± 0.77	45.69 ± 14.11	32.96 ± 4.67
Thin-Film	16.03 ± 0.34	2.00 ± 0.65	32.03 ± 10.24	32.96 ± 4.67

3. Discussion

Solar Irradiance, Temperature and Power Output

The result (as shown in Table 1) showed that the daily environmental conditions including solar irradiance and temperature had a direct influence on the power output of the three solar panel types assessed in this study. Solar

irradiance ranged from 313.4 W/m² (Day 2) to 838.7 W/m² (Day 7), while temperatures varied between 27.8°C and 39.5°C. Correspondingly, monocrystalline panels produced the highest output (72.51 W on Day 7), followed by polycrystalline (66.39 W) and thin-film panels (47.99 W) (Figure1). The lowest outputs were recorded on Day 2 across all technologies, with monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and thin-film producing 29.39 W, 24.39 W, and 15.7 W,

respectively. This trend aligns with previous photovoltaic performance to environmental findings that underscore the sensitivity of inputs (Shaker *et al.*, 2024; Zhou *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 1: *Daily power output of monocrystalline, polycrystalline, and thin-film solar panels over a 7-day period.*

A key trend observed in Table 1 is the consistent correlation between higher irradiance and increased power output, with Day 7 clearly standing out as the day with the highest irradiance (838.7 W/m^2) and power generation across all panel types. The monocrystalline panel not only achieved the highest output but also demonstrated superior performance consistency across the range of irradiance values. On average, monocrystalline panels yielded 53.80 W , compared to 45.12 W for polycrystalline and 32.60 W for thin-film (Table 3). This is consistent with the previous studies which

established that monocrystalline technology has more efficiency under high irradiance (Chow, 2018; Feurer, 2017). Thin-film panels consistently delivered the lowest outputs (Figure 2), underscoring its relatively lower efficiency, particularly under intense solar conditions. These patterns reinforce the notion that material composition and cell structure significantly affect photovoltaic yield, and they support technology-specific deployment strategies in regions with varying solar potential (Makrides *et al.*, 2010; Skoplaki and Palyvos, 2009).

Figure 2: Scatter plots with regression lines showing the relationship between solar irradiance and power output for three types of solar panels.

Environmental factors, especially temperature, also influenced panel performance in notable ways. For instance, despite similar high temperatures on Days 1 (39.3°C) and 2 (39.5°C), the lower irradiance on Day 2 (313.4 W/m²) (Figure 3) may have further exacerbated performance loss across all panels. Temperature-induced efficiency decline was especially evident for monocrystalline panels, which typically have higher negative temperature coefficients (Xu *et al.*, 2024). This implies that while monocrystalline panels generally outperform

others, their performance is more sensitive to thermal stress. Additionally, the sharp drop in outputs on Day 2 may be attributed to both thermal effects and potential anomalies like atmospheric dust, shading, or soiling, which can significantly reduce irradiance penetration (Chaichan and Kazem, 2024; Kazem *et al.*, 2014). These insights are crucial for optimizing photovoltaic installations in hot climates, where both irradiance and temperature vary unpredictably and can jointly influence system efficiency.

Figure 3: Dual-axis line plot showing daily variation in solar irradiance and ambient temperature.

Voltage and Current

The result in Table 2 demonstrated that monocrystalline solar panels consistently produced the highest voltage across all seven days, ranging from 18.20 V to 18.72 V. This superior voltage performance is linked to the high-purity silicon used in monocrystalline cells, which enables efficient energy conversion under direct sunlight (Li *et al.*, 2024). Polycrystalline panels showed moderate

voltage outputs, while thin-film panels recorded the lowest, ranging between 15.56 V and 16.47 V (Figure 4). Their lower voltage performance is associated with their amorphous structure, which, though cost-effective and flexible, underperforms in high irradiance (Ahmad, 2025). The voltage trends corresponded with irradiance patterns in Table 1, especially on Days 6 and 7. This further highlights the technological advantage of monocrystalline panels in maintaining voltage stability under fluctuating solar conditions.

Figure 4: Daily Voltage Output for Monocrystalline, Polycrystalline, and Thin-Film Solar Panels

Current output result (Table 2; Figure 5) further reinforced that monocrystalline and polycrystalline have better performance, peaking at 3.90 A and at 3.71 A respectively on high-irradiance days, while thin-film peaked at only 3.04 A. On low irradiance days like Day 2, thin-film panels dropped to 0.98 A, underlining their limited adaptability to suboptimal sunlight (Chowdhury *et al.*, 2020).

Table 3 also confirms that monocrystalline panels have the highest average power output (53.80 ± 15.05 W), voltage (18.49 ± 0.20 V), and current (2.91 ± 0.80 A), under uniform temperature conditions (32.96 ± 4.67 °C). This low standard deviation in voltage signifies

greater stability, in contrast to thin-film panels, which not only recorded the lowest average power (32.03 ± 10.24 W) but also the highest variability, indicating inconsistent performance (Khanam *et al.*, 2021). Since temperature was constant across all panel types, it is evident that the differences in performance are material-driven (Ayadi *et al.*, 2022). In practical terms, monocrystalline panels are best suited for regions with high power demand and warm climates like Nigeria. Polycrystalline panels present a cost-efficient alternative with moderate performance, while thin-film panels may not be ideal for applications requiring high or stable power output.

Figure 5: Current Output for Monocrystalline, Polycrystalline, and Thin-Film Solar Panels

Conclusion

Based on the experimental results, this study concludes that monocrystalline solar panels deliver the highest and most consistent power output under natural sunlight. Across the seven-day observation period, monocrystalline panels consistently outperformed polycrystalline and thin-film technologies in terms of voltage, current, and overall power output. Polycrystalline panels showed moderate performance, striking a balance between cost and output, while thin-film panels exhibited the lowest and most variable power generation, making them less reliable under fluctuating irradiance levels. The study also showed that material composition, rather than temperature, was the dominant factor influencing performance. Statistical analysis further confirmed monocrystalline panels as the most consistent and reliable option, especially in warm, high-irradiance environments such as Nigeria. Therefore, for practical applications where stable and efficient solar power generation is required, monocrystalline panels are most suitable.

Polycrystalline panels may be considered for budget-conscious projects with moderate performance expectations, while thin-film panels are better suited for low-power or niche applications where flexibility and lightweight design are more critical than output consistency.

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